

Reactions of Methylene (CHT) with Ethylene in the Presence of Perfluorobutadiene*

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Methylene-t from the photolysis of tritiated ketene (CHT=CO) has been reacted with ethylene and perfluorobutadiene in the absence and presence of molecular oxygen at constant total pressure of 710 Torr. The radioactive yields of HT+C₂H₃T, propylene, and cyclopropane have been measured for each experiment. Increasing the pressure of perfluorobutadiene had drastically reduced the over-all activity of all labeled by tritium products. The presence of molecular oxygen (triplet methylene scavenger) reduced the percentage yield of cyclopropane by a factor of about two but enhanced slightly that of propylene and considerably of HT+C₂H₃T. The percentage yield of HT+C₂H₃T increased with increasing pressure of perfluorobutadiene, while that of cyclopropane has decreased. Yields of propylene-t did not show a uniform variation with pressure, but it was all times larger than that of cyclopropane-t. f_{Δ} ratio was constant when plotted against C₄F₆ pressure.

We failed to arrive at one of the major aims of this research: the detection of tritiated perfluorobutadiene (one fluorine atom had supposed to be replaced by a tritium atom).

Products of insertion, addition, or reaction of CHT with perfluorobutadiene were not found at all.

REACTIONS of methylene have been studied in the gas phase with hydrogen, methane^{1,5} ethylene², mercury 6 (³P₁) photosensitized decomposition of cyclobutanone³, and with different substrates⁴. Others than the mechanism accounting for the formation of HT, CH₂=CHT, propylene-t and cyclopropane-t, there was always the singlet-triplet CHT species which lead to the formation of this or that compound. Strongly-related to the later point is the propylene-t to cyclopropane-t ratio and its dependence on the entire pressure. Some authors² had reported that 71% of all CHT species formed in the direct photolysis of CHT=CO are singlet ones, while the triplets form 29%. Others³ have stated that 10.5% of the products arise from a singlet pathway after a photosensitized decomposition of cyclobutanone. Although Russell had Rowland⁴ thought once that the molecular hydrogen had occasionally been reported (in the absence of O₂) without identification of its origin, Laufer⁵ presented the following molecular hydrogen-producing reactions :-

walter [5,6] has attributed the formation of molecular hydrogen to the overall sequence of the photolysis of ketene at 2139 Å :-

All these pathways are reasonable though no one had ever seen the free carbon which might be liberated

viareaction (b). Same situation concerning C₂O formed by reaction (c). No doubt that HT could be formed instead of H₂ in reactions (b) and (c) if CHT and CHTCO were available instead of CH₂ and CH₂CO respectively.

There is a great doubt regarding the probability of occurrence of reaction (d) proposed by Walter [6], since the analogous reaction in our case (CHTCO) must accordingly assume either of the following forms :

No one had been up to date able to discover CHT=CHT and/or C₂HT.

Experimental

Philips research grade ethylene was used without further purification. Ketene-t was prepared by the pyrolysis of acetic anhydride-t and stored at liquid nitrogen temperature^{1,4,7}. Perfluorobutadiene (CF₂=CF-CF=CF₂) has been isolated and purified gas chromatographically. A special trap at 196° was used for isolating and collecting perfluorobutadiene. The collected fractions were stored in a pyrex bulb at room temperature. Gas pressures were measured on a Model FA-141 Wallace-Tiernan Inc. mechanical dial manometer. The reactants were subsequently transferred to the cylindrical photolysis cell attached to a mercury and grease-free vacuum system (Pyrex, greasless Springham Viton A diaphragm valves). The cell, constructed of

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Unscavenged by molecular oxygen experiments of (R. Russell and Rowland⁴ had shown no HT at all ethylene pressure was constant 196 cm. Hg). They have found a relative radioactivity yield of 0.01 for CH₃T (methane) in all runs that contained ethylene with or without molecular oxygen. The presence of some oxygen enhanced the relative yield of tritiated hydrogen. Some thing has been observed in our results. We should note that the considerable increase in HT+C₂H₃T yield occurred after the addition of 10 Torr oxygen was constantly accompanied by a simultaneous decrease in the yield of cyclopropane-t. This significant finding can be accounted for by the reaction pathway presented in [4], involving reaction of oxygen (as a scavenger) with triplet methylene (³CHT) resulting in the formation of labeled hydrogen :

On this basis one can understand why the presence of oxygen suppressed yielded of acyclopropane-t, by interaction with triplet methylene as a precursor which ordinarily leads to the formations of cyclopropane-t.

Oxygen seems to be an inert constituent with regard to singlet methylene. Hence it cannot affect that part of cyclopropane-t formed by the direct reaction of singlet methylene with double bond of CH₂=CH₂ (reaction 6).

C, Propylene-Cyclopropane duality :

If we take into account the conclusions drawn by authors of reference 2 regarding the 29% yield of triplet methylene and 71% yield of singlet CHT species arising from the 3130 Å photolysis of CHT=CO and, in addition, the well-established fact that triplet methylene yield is a pressure dependent one^{8,9}, one can immediately understand that not all singlet methylene species lead to the formation of tritiated propylene, but they may make tritiated cyclopropane contributions, depending on the way that singlet CHT reacts separately with C-H and C=C bonds.

The pressure-dependent isomerization process of cyclopropane-t to propylene-t, and thus enhancing the ultimate yield of propylene-t at the account of the former, was confirmed by the work published^{2,3}. Our results tell something else :

1. Yield of HT+C₂H₃T varied with varying pressure of ethylene (Table 1 and 2). Dependence is an inverse one. Yields of ethylene found by Montague and Rowland³ did not show pressure-dependence.
2. Yield of cyclopropane-t, but not of propylene-t, had shown a pressure-dependence character. It increased with increasing pressure of ethylene added. The addition of 10 Torr of molecular oxygen had made a further reduction in the yield of cyclopropane-t. The presence of oxygen as a triplet methylene scavenger raised the yields of both HT+C₂H₃T and that of propylene-t.

3. $f_{\Delta} = \frac{\Delta}{\text{propylene} + \Delta} \rightarrow$ ratio plotted against ethylene in

reference 2 increased as ethylene's pressure increased, but is not a linear one.

f_{Δ} found by us was constant over a pressure range of perfluorobutadiene of 0-355 Torr (range of ethylene pressure was 700-348 Torr). A plot of this ratio against C_4F_6 pressure is shown in Fig. 3.

One important comment can be made concerning the way that Lee and Rowland² had drawn f_{Δ} values against ethylene pressure. They certainly were able to make a linear plot between the six points that they had found.

4. Sum of all C_3 products³ is found to be equal to $89.2 \pm 0.5\%$, while that found by us is slightly more than 93% of all registered tritium activity, over a C_4F_6 pressure range of 0.0-177 Torr (Table 2).

These main and sharp differences can solely be attributed to the presence of perfluorobutadiene. The mechanism of interaction seems to be at present a mysterious one.

The constancy of f_{Δ} ratio may be explained as follows :

The presence of perfluorobutadiene cancels out the effect of ethylene on propylene-t only, in such a way that its yield remains unfluenced by the variation of C_2H_4 pressure. But why does perfluorobutadiene have such an influence upon propylene-t and having no effect on cyclopropane-t? Let us examine the following critical balance which takes into account the collisional deactivation process which rises with increasing pressure of ethylene and thus increasing yield of cyclopropane-t and consequently decreasing yield of propylene-t. From Table 2 it is apparent that yield of HT + C_2H_3T and that of propylene-t rise or fall together, and when they rise, yield of cyclopropane-t falls, and vice versa. The following scheme illustrating this balance shows that isomerization of cyclopropane-t to propylene-t (a pressure-dependent process) is actually not the unique fate of a vibrationally excited cyclopropane-t molecule but at some higher excitation energies (threshold is unknown, but can be roughly estimated) it decomposes giving rise to an equally distributed yields of CHT and C_2H_3T since CHT and the other two CH_2 species are uniformly oriented through the plane of Cyclopropane molecule.

Our results (Table 1) confirm this decomposition mechanism which is (like the isomerisation process) also a pressure-dependent one.

Although this decomposition scheme yields an additional tritiated ethylene which has been registered altogether with HT, it is impossible at present to say which yield is larger.

To elucidate this point one must perform a sharp identification of both HT and C_2H_3T using some other columns. Quantitative measurements of both thermal conductivity (mass) peaks of C_2H_4 and C_2H_3T can give a precise evaluation for the occurrence probability of the two possible pathways.

D Quenching Effect of Perfluorobutadiene :

Passing through the proportional counter, perfluorobutadiene had drastically suppressed the external source (Cs-137) activity. Moreover, it had reduced the total activity of each run as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The reduction effect increased as its pressure increased, and at higher pressures an almost complete activity annihilation took place. No scientific explanation is available right now, except that the presence of six fluorine atoms with a great electron affinity can in some way physically interact with the central filament (the anode), thus minimizing the counting efficiency of the counter. Similar observation had been noted by some authors more than ten years ago¹⁰, while working on same nitrocompounds. Others¹¹ found that even benzene (C_6H_6) displayed a similar self-quenching or 'negative' effect, but to a much less extent.

This difficulty had been overcome by applying an efficient thin-window proportional counter¹². The window of this counter is completely insulated from the following vapors.

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